

Enhancing Plant Growth: The Importance of LED Lighting in Greenhouse and Hydroponic Systems

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Introduction

Integrating light-emitting diode (LED) lighting systems in greenhouse and plant hydroponic culture represents a significant stride towards sustainable agriculture. This study explores the pivotal role of LED technology, particularly for purple, blue, and red light in nurturing to enhance plant growth and development. Plant photoreceptors absorb different wavelengths of light and activate a signaling cascade from upstream to downstream that will activate several complex physiological processes and morphogenesis. Red light (R, 620–700 nm) is recognized by phytochrome which controls photomorphogenesis via promoting vegetative and generative growth and development including germination, flowering and fruiting. On the other hand, blue light (B, 445–500 nm) is recognized by cryptochromes which stimulate photosynthesis, chlorophyll - carotenoids biosynthesis, and stomatal opening. In terms of nutritional quality, applying B light to plants can increase the accumulation of anthocyanins, carotenoids, and ascorbic acid contents. R lights determine better growth compared to B lights. Furthermore, adding B light to R light as a combination at low intensity can prevent excessive etiolation and reactivate chlorophyll synthesis. In addition, it has been reported that the combination of R and B light increases the development of photosynthetic apparatus, accumulation of biomass, forming more compact plant structure and inhibits flowering. The efficiency of absorption and assimilation of macro and micronutrients in hydroponic systems is also stimulated by the combination of R and B light. Combining R and B in balanced percentages can form purple light fixtures. Purple light is commonly used in the early stages of growth to induce seed germination, cell division and shoot regeneration. A combination of R and B light for LED lighting in the greenhouse and hydroponic culture systems may provide improved control of the crop growing environment and reduce pollutant emissions, producing a homogeneous and high-quality crop, time efficient and low-cost production with predictable results. Through this farming strategy, LED-equipped facilities maximize spatial efficiency and become a solution for obtaining efficient yields and high nutritional value, thus providing a strong case for integrating them into future modern agricultural practices.

Keywords: LED lighting, hydroponic systems, greenhouse, plant growth, agriculture

Introduction

Light is one of the fundamental components of the environment that influences a plant's growth and development. The energy required for carbohydrate synthesis in the photosynthesis process that occurs on chloroplasts component is obtained from light. Light also plays a key role as a morphogenic signal and controls biochemical reactions to regulate various functional and structural responses in plants. Therefore, the quality of light greatly influences plant development. Different colours of light wavelength have varying energy sources for plant growth. It may be possible to alter the durations, intensities, and light range spectrum in artificial growth environments. Nevertheless, not every full range of light spectrums is advantageous. In general, only visible spectrum radiation gets absorbed by plants to carry out their physiological processes. Since the beginning of the 20th century, it has been globally confirmed that light in the visible spectrum with wavelengths between 400-700 nm is called photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and is part of the light spectrum that is favourable to plants to use for photosynthesis, flowering, and photomorphogenesis. Plants absorb the light spectrum through some photoreceptors, including phytochromes (which capture far-red/red light), cryptochromes (which absorb blue light and ultraviolet A radiation), and others [1,2]. Red (R) and blue (B) lights are reported to have the most significant effects on plant development [3]. A single photoreceptor regulates certain

plant physiology reactions, whereas other functions are controlled by many photoreceptors operating simultaneously [4]. Recently, emerging technologies such as LED lights that offer multiple visible colours have become increasingly popular and much attention has been paid to this research. Due to this, LED illumination might supply PAR. Several studies demonstrated that the manipulation of LED light wavelengths for plant cultivation can increase the efficiency of crop production [1,5].

Artificial lighting for crop production has been researched since 1860, although there are still limited practical applications for it. In 1962, the first red light-emitting diode (LED) was produced.

Then, in 2000, Japan made history by being the first country to widely and commercially employ LED for several plant species. LED can select specific wavelengths and light spectra to investigate the role of light quality in plant growth [5,6]. It was reported that LED technology enables more energy efficiency results and uses less electricity than other conventional lamps [7]. Several studies have shown that the wavelength and quality of light produced by LED may promote the activation of enzymes and enhance the build-up of bioactive compounds [5]. Besides that, taking into consideration the consequences of climate change leading to significant decreases in agricultural production, as well as in geographic areas with little sunlight during winter, it can be improved through manipulation of the use of LED light in greenhouses and hydroponic plant cultivation with optimization of broad-spectrum emissions to the quality and productivity of plants. The effects of LED light quality are more complex, and inconsistent outcomes were frequently reported. This still needs to be followed regarding the specifications of the spectrum wavelengths for each different plant species [1].

Therefore, in this review article, we will explore and discuss current research data concerning the important role of integrating the usage of LED technology in greenhouses and hydroponic systems. Several different LED light wavelengths (purple, red, blue, and their combination) were mentioned based on their influence on plant growth and development for sustainable agriculture.

The Types of LED

LED are solid-state semiconductors that emit light through electroluminescence, a process that sets them apart from other light sources. Compared to traditional lighting alternatives, LED presents a range of advantages for usage in crop production systems. The advantages of LED are small microchips lead to easily adjustable and positionable, highly efficient, with low power consumption and energy usage, long-lasting, safe to handle, emit low temperatures, compact, capable of selecting specific wavelengths without requiring filters, leading to reduced energy costs, and providing uniform lighting [5]. Other research studies have also indicated that LED are more durable compared to other types of lamps using filaments, pressurized gas, or mercury in glass. LED are well-suited for use in low temperatures (down to -40°C) and high humidity conditions. This characteristic makes LED lighting technology a highly beneficial option for cultivating plant growth, offering the potential for consistent, abundant annual harvests with minimal limitations. By providing continuous light exposure to plants, LED promote accelerated growth and development [2]. In addition, due to these distinctive properties LED lights can be used effectively as either a supplementary or primary lighting source to increase the yield and quality of crop production in a greenhouse environment [7].

The use of LED lights in growing plants in controlled environment has been proven to overcome the difficulties faced by other traditional lamp sources such as High-Pressure Sodium lamps (HPS), fluorescent lamps, High-intensity discharge (HID) lamps, metal halide (MH) lamps and others, which is a lamp that has been frequently used for over last decades. These conventional light sources have a number of drawbacks such as a high operating temperature a large volume and a significant energy requirement. They are also not environmentally friendly due to their CO_2 emissions and light pollution [2]. In tomato production, it is proven that average daily energy consumption shows significant energy savings using LED lighting technology (31 kWh per day) compared to HPS lighting (129 kWh per day) [8]. The use of LED lighting may require higher initial costs and indicate inconsistent product quality between growers in determining the lighting needs of certain crops. However, the flexibility of LED light control is superior in that it allows significantly reducing energy losses and controlling plant growth, thereby achieving improvements in two key parameters in one action and ultimately being much more energy and cost efficient [6].

LED have some different types based on wavelength red, blue, green, purple, white and combination of them. However, many reports from previous experiments in recent times have shown that the red and blue regions of the light spectrum are the most effective for plant growth and development in a specific wavelength. Each type of LED has different physiology effects on plant that can be clearly seen and differentiated, although some of them are overlap [1-4, 9-11].

Red light LED is generally associated with controls photomorphogenesis via promoting vegetative and generative growth and development including germination, flowering and fruiting. More specifically, red light regulates the growth rate of biomass and plant production, increase stem elongation and branching, dry weight, concentration of soluble protein, reproduction, efficient in improving nutritional quality which associated with increasing phenol and anthocyanin content, and delay or inhibit the plant's transition to flowering in early stage (Figure 1.). In addition, it is also known that red light can also increase plant yields by reducing nitrates and increasing plant vitamin C [2]. Previous experiments on kale research demonstrated that the enormous rise in plant height and fresh stem weight was precisely caused by light in the red region of the spectrum [5]. Similar results were also obtained by providing pure R light on the early growth of tomato plants which showed that plant height, leaf area, cotyledon expansion, and hypocotyl elongation were improves all these parameters well. This is because pure R lights have the ability to respond to shadow avoidance on seedlings. However, these changes resulted in a strong decrease in the values of low photosynthetic capacity and photochemical activity, compared with the RB combination treatment [12].

The effect of red light on plant height was also reported for lettuce and kale which showed a significant increase when providing 100% R:0% B light. Providing 90% R light and above can significantly increase the fresh and dry mass of some plants in several plants such as lettuce, spinach, basil, kale, and pepper [9]. In *Hypericum perforatum* L.cv. Topa's research results showed that the application of 100% R light greatly influenced the increase in plant height, fresh and dry weight, number and diameter of flowers, number of vegetative (17) and reproductive shoots (8.33), and relative leaf water content reaches up to 83.84%. Thus, it also verifies that red light induces cell division and expansion [13]. Increasing the proportion of red light (25% to 75%) in Lettuce positively impacts the fresh shoot biomass, which continues to increase [14]. However, generally, plants grown under higher R light fractions have slight pale green spreading leaves with long petioles and poor-quality fruit pigmentation. Therefore, this confirms the function of another type of light, blue light instead of red light, which affects the dark green colour of plant leaves [9].

Blue light wavelength is generally considered a critical growth regulator because it is responsible for the opening of stomata, stomatal density, chlorophyll-carotene biosynthesis, chloroplast development, leaf expansion, leading to compact plant morphological structure, improving photosynthetic capacity and nitrogen content, resulting in maximum transpiration rate (Figure 1.) [6]. It is also involved in the processes of phototropism and photomorphogenesis [12]. The density and configuration of chloroplasts controlled in plant leaves are important for enhancing photosynthetic light harvesting. Whereas, stomatal conductance is a crucial parameter to maximize the efficiency of CO₂ and water exchange processes [2]. In addition, in comparison to other light treatments, this light is also highly effective at inducing the amount of Rubisco, pigments, and photochemical efficiency, which have been widely reported to be able to improve the physiological performance of several tomato seedlings [12], strawberry [15], *Hypericum perforatum* L. cv. [13], lettuce and cucumbers [6]. Moreover, research on strawberries conducted by [15] reported that the application of All blue light from the various peak LED types (405, 450, and 470 nm) can also promote more flowering compared with red light (630 and 660 nm). Therefore, blue light irradiation during the seeding period can speed up the harvest.

The combination of R and B LED lights is a new strategy that is increasingly being used and chosen both in research and commercial cultivation because it shows effectiveness as a better light source in encouraging plant development and increasing production yields. The main goal of this combination is to combine the advantages of both and reduce the impact of losses. In general, combining these two colours can have an effect on increasing photosynthesis, biomass accumulation, forming a more compact plant structure and inhibit flowering in early stage (Figure 1.) [2]. Some differences manipulate the R and B LED percentages to achieve optimization for each plant species, especially on horticulture plants. The interaction of light in determining photomorphogenesis in most plant species given a combination of 25% blue and 75% red LED regulate positive results, such as shorter shoots and hypocotyls, longer roots, and fresh-weight roots, more compact stem structure with a larger diameter and fewer morphological abnormalities [7]. It was even reported that, research with a lower proportion of blue light LED R 3: 1 B in greenhouse of tomato plants in the Mediterranean was also significantly increase yield and fruit quality [16].

Table 1. A small percentage of blue light added to red light in some types of plants

Crop Plant	LED R & B Ratio	Plant Growth and Development	References
Lilium, Chrysanthemum and tomato	7:3	Increase fresh weight and dry weight shoot and root, reduced hypocotyl and shoot height, more compact stem structure with a larger diameter, fewer morphological abnormalities	[2]
Pepper, kale, basil, lettuce, and spinach	B light: a) 5% - 9% b) 9% - 17%	a) The biomass, the number leaves and accumulation of chlorophyll b) Carotenoid contents and antioxidant levels	[9]
Tomato seedlings in grafting cultivation	70% R+30% B	Improvement in seed quality (total leaf area, shoot and root dry weight, total chlorophyll-carotenoids, soluble protein and sugar content) and grafting success both pre- and post-grafting	[17]
Tomatoes	95% R+5% B	Induce earlier tomato fruit production, 75% higher number of nodes, tomatoes fruit and total fresh weight	[8]
Tomato plants in the early seedling stages	60% R+ 40% B	Photosynthesis and biomass production	[12]
Basil	60% R+ 40% B	The fresh biomass of leaves and shoots	[18]

Blue LED can be a combination of red light in a small proportion. It was reported that adding B light to R light as a combination at low intensity can prevent excessive hypocotyl etiolation and reactivate chlorophyll synthesis [5, 2]. In tomato plants, it can also positively regulate transpiration, keep shoot grafts from drying out quickly and increase the number of shoots in grafting cultivation [11]. Other research on tomato plants showed a more detailed increase in some of carotenoid types such as phytoene, lycopene, -carotene content in fruits, followed by an increase in photosynthesis, plant growth and fruit weight [19]. Based on several previous studies shown in Table. 1 it can be assumed that the additional optimization of blue light at a low percentage combined with R light diverse depending on the plant species and growth stage. This is further supported by research studies on basil (*Ocimum basilicum* var. 'Genovese') which show that treatment B with higher ratio (60B/40R) causes a reduction in leaf dry biomass of 30%, compared to treatments 30B/70R and 40B/60R [18]. Excessive blue LED illumination from standard capacity, typically the lowest stem diameter, generates oxygen radicals, suppresses growth, plants produce smaller and causes photoinhibition in indoor farming [1, 12, 13]. However, in contrast, research on *Cichorium endivia* L reported that the higher the proportion of blue light compared other light, the better growth of this plant in terms of number of leaves and carotene [20]. Therefore, the effect of the proportion of combined application of B and R LED lights varies on the growth and development of each type and variety of plant.

Combining R and B in balanced percentages can form purple light fixtures. Purple light is commonly used in the early stages of growth to induce seed germination, cell division and shoot regeneration (Figure 1.) [21]. The growth parameters consistently increased under extra LED light in cucumbers cultivated in greenhouses with or without light integration using LED at the same percentage variable R:B ratio and two daily light integrals [2]. Research on the plant *Hypericum perforatum* L.cv. Topaz exposed to LED with an R50:B50 ratio showed results showing that the dark gland area increased significantly and the stomatal density was higher, reaching 85% [13]. Other research also evidence that, the size and weight of peppers are significantly increased when red and blue light wavelengths are combined (1:1), compared to monochromatic light. Moreover, it was also reported that purple light can improve plant health by increasing the content of phytochemicals including: capsaicinoids, proteins and carotenoids, as well as controlling the bright colour of fruit development [22].

Figure 1. LED Lighting in Greenhouse and Hydroponic Systems

Recognition of Light by Plant Receptors

Light consists of tiny packets of energy called photons. Compared to low energy photons, high energy photons have a shorter wavelength. The full range of these photons is called the electromagnetic spectrum. However, for growth and development, plants only utilize the visible spectrum, which spans 400–700 nm [1]. Due to the sessile nature of plants, they have developed high networks of photoreceptors that recognize various light wavelengths that will activate a signalling cascade from upstream to downstream that will trigger a number of intricate physiological functions as well as morphogenesis. These cascades originate from gene expression and ultimately trigger a variety of physiological processes [11].

Based on the wavelengths absorb, the biological system of a plant normally consists of five class of photoreceptors. Different classes of photoreceptors recognize appropriate and specific wavelengths, phytochromes (PHY) which act effectively to absorb light in the red (620–700 nm) and far red (700–800 nm) wavelength ranges; three distinct types of photoreceptor proteins, consisting of phototropin (PHOTO), cryptochromes (CRY) and the zeitlupes (ZLT)/FKF1/LKP2 complex actively perceive light in the blue (445-500 nm) and the UV-A (315-400 nm) regions; and on the other hand, the UVB-Resistance locus 8 (UVR8) photoreceptors capture light strongly in the UV-B (280-315 nm) areas [1, 2, 11]. It is also well-acknowledged that, certain of higher plants are able to composed some of photoreceptor, such as: two phototropins (phot₁ and phot₂), three cryptochromes (cry₁-cry₃), all types of phytochromes (phy A-phy E), and one UVR8 photoreceptor [2].

The phytochrome family is the leading group and plays a significant role in plant physiology. PHY is a soluble protein that functions as a chromophore by binding phytochromobilin. There are four different kinds of phytochrome isoforms in angiosperm plants: phy A, B, C/F, and E. Other forms of phy are present in green plants with lighted, but PhyA often accumulates in etiolated seeds. Photoperiodism is a mechanism by which red light phytochromes can transition from their inactive "red" form to the physiologically active "far red" form. Phytochromes are found in the cytoplasm in their inactive red form. While they are active, they partially migrate into the nucleus, altering the expression levels of many genes. Phytochromes play a role in regulating seed germination, de-etiolation, shade avoidance, circadian rhythms, and flowering induction [2]. According to plant model studies in

Arabidopsis, two forms of cryptochromes (Cry₁, Cry₂) and phototropins (Phot₁, Phot₂) have been identified. A covalent bond is created between the chromophore and the photoreceptor apoprotein when cryptochrome molecules absorb blue/UV-A light. This process involves intramolecular redox, which modifies the receptor apoprotein's structure and sets off a signalling cascade that alters gene expression by removing Cry₁ from the nucleus and breaking down Cry₂. Another newly found plant photoreceptor that monomerizes the initial photoreceptor dimers is called UVR8 (UV RESISTANT LOCUS 8) [4].

In various cases reported that, upon interaction between phytochrome, cryptochrome, or UV-B receptor UVR8 and major protein regulators of photomorphogenesis, such as COP1 protein and E3-ubiquitin ligase, several photoreceptors signalling pathways will be interlock and overlap. Therefore, finding precise and ideal wavelengths for all plant species is currently exceedingly challenging due to the sensitivity and complexity of plant responses to light signals [1, 4, 11].

LED Regulates Several Plant Physiological Processes

The quality of light will affect to the several plant physiological processes. The application of red and blue LED lights to plants significantly increasing the quantity of strong chlorophyll absorption in plants, thereby increasing photosynthesis and allowing plants to absorb more light energy [1]. Particularly, blue light absorbed by cryptochrome is largely responsible for controlling stomatal conductance and chlorophyll-carotenoids biosynthesis [2]. The size, quantity, and arrangement of stomata on the upper and bottom surfaces of leaves also affect a plant's potential to absorb light [1]. The range of light signals PPF (Photosynthetic photon flux density influence) also plays a widely important role to plant development. Plant growth can frequently be most effectively stimulated by PPF values in the range of 200–250 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$ to 500–800 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$ [1]. Red pak choi and mustard plants have been shown to have higher leaf chlorophyll index with higher PPF irradiation (545–440 $\mu\text{mol m}^2\text{s}$) compared to lower PPF irradiation (220 $\mu\text{mol m}^2\text{s}$). In contrast, for hydroponic production of lettuce plants, a PFD of 200 $\mu\text{mol m}^2\text{s}$ with a 16 h/d photoperiod provided by LED with an R:B ratio of 2:2 was appropriate [23]. Numerous research has revealed that growing lettuce at illumination levels of more than 600 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$ would result in a loss in chlorophyll and total plant biomass as well as an increase in disease in the upper leaves [4]. As a result, no ideal PPF level value has yet been identified for each plant development.

The increase in chlorophyll concentration is also strongly influenced by differences proportion of the combination of R and B LED lighting. Several reports on tomato plants with LED combinations of 88% R and 12% B light [1] or R7:B3 [17] show that there is a more effective increase in the value of PSII Y(II) photochemistry, photochemical quenching (qP), and electron transport rate (ETR) which indicates that photosynthetic performance can work better than the control. Another research [24] also reported the same result that adding 7% blue light to *Cucumis sativus* showed the ability to photosynthesize was twice as great in leaves. [3] stated that in terms of increasing photosynthesis, only 2 LED combinations in the form of R: B alone works better than adding up to 3 or 4 other light combinations. This is because only red and blue light have the best synergistic effect.

The production of bioactive chemicals and antioxidants in plants is also significantly influenced by lighting conditions, making it one of the most significant elements. Various LED lights have varied effects on synthesis of primer (like proteins, carbohydrate, and vitamins) and secondary metabolic content (anthocyanins, flavonoids, polyphenols and etc). These bioactive substances will affect the plant's quality, flavour, and aroma. Even after harvest, plant metabolite synthesis may be effectively stimulated by LED irradiation [5-6]. In general, giving LED B lights to plants can increase the accumulation of anthocyanin, carotenoid and ascorbic acid content. Meanwhile, the application of red LED light causes an increase in the accumulation of phenol, polyphenol and flavonoid content. Apart from that, it was reported that the content of bioactive compounds can also be increased through purple LED. This treatment was carried out on two varieties of *Ocimum basilicum* which caused an increase in the content of anthocyanins, phenols and carotenoids [5]. It is supported by research in Lettuce that also seems to react positively to R light with several positive effects on nutritional and antioxidant values which phenol and flavonoid increase significantly, but reduce the concentration of ascorbic acid. Meanwhile, addition with B light increases anthocyanins reach up to 31% [6]. However, in *Hypericum perforatum* L. cv plant the total flavonoid content interacted positively with the provision of 100% blue light, not red light [13]. In *Cichorium endivia* L showed that the higher proportion of blue can also able to increase Vitamin C [20]. As a result, each plant's response to LEDs' nutritional quality is distinctive. These bioactive chemicals are engaged in several biological functions, such as plant coloration, defence against ultraviolet (UV) radiation and infectious agents, protection of leaf cells from photooxidative damage, and reaction to ROS-induced oxidative stress [5].

Practical Usage of LED Technology in Green Houses and Hydroponic Systems

The wavelength of LED light also increases the effectiveness of macro- and micronutrient absorption and assimilation in hydroponic systems, which leads to a higher rise in plant biomass. B and R LED lights are actively involved in nutrient uptake and assimilation through complex signal transduction pathways [11]. According to a recent study, lettuce enhances the absorption of N, K, Ca, and Mg when exposed to spectrum LED red light in the 620–700 nm region [6]. These results corroborate earlier studies on lettuce shoots which demonstrated greater levels of N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Mn, and Zn with 1R1B treatment. Whereas, lettuce with a 75% B light ratio treatment made it easier to compare C content than other light treatments [14]. A combination red and blue in tomato plant can improve K accumulation and absorption [19]. Furthermore, hydroponically grown for basil plants with a light ratio of 3R: 1B exhibited increased absorption of macronutrients N, P, K, Ca, Fe, and Mg [11]. While basil applied of 50B/50R & 10B/90R LED also elevated levels of Ca & B (Boron). For cell division and cell wall formation, boron is largely beneficial [18].

Crop production systems in enclosed spaces such as greenhouses are growing rapidly and widely. Energy is one of the components that has a significant influence on the cost increase of 20-30% of the overall cost of crop production in greenhouses. The construction of greenhouses in areas with poor lighting and variable photoperiods (day length), it is important to consider energy use to be more cost-effective [7]. Due to their high energy efficiency for photosynthesis, ease of control over the spectrum composition, low radiant heat transfer, and ease of adjusting light intensity to plant photoreceptors, LED light sources are a useful way to lower production costs in greenhouses and improve agricultural output with shorter harvest cycles [11].

The practical use of LED technology, especially R and B lights, in greenhouse growing environments and hydroponic systems is a profitable strategy because this integration can be designed anywhere as it does not require soil and solar radiation; is not affected by climate change factors; accelerate plant growth due to increased high energy efficiency for photosynthesis and high absorption of resources (water, minerals, macro, and microelements, etc.); produces compact, healthy and quality plants with a longer shelf life; sustainable production; predictable results; reducing production time and reducing pollutant emissions. In addition, this integrated system can also create a homogeneous and efficient production environment with low costs, low lamp surface temperatures, high light utilization efficiency, and a wide light spectrum [11]. The selection of the right LED light wavelength intensity for each plant species determines the success of functional production and increases significant maintenance cost savings in the long term [2]. Currently, various LED models with reflectors that form a stream of light are growing rapidly in production, including conical, tubular, and other forms. The design in the form of an LED tube is the most efficient for lighting plants because the longer the tube, the higher the PPF efficiency (mmol/J). In addition, when designing LEDs, the distance between the lamp and the plant must be considered because it can result in the formation of necrosis and chlorosis spots on the shoots [4].

Conclusion

Integrating LED lighting systems in greenhouse and plant hydroponic culture represents a significant stride towards sustainable agriculture. LED are highly efficient, with low power consumption and energy usage. It can used as primary or supplemental lighting sources. Many reports from previous experiments have shown that the best performances were observed under a combination of red or blue lights. The combination of Red and Blue LED is the most effective for plant growth: it can increase photosynthesis, biomass accumulation, more compact plant structure, inhibit flowering, prevent excessive etiolation and reactivate chlorophyll synthesis, increase efficiency of absorption and assimilation of macro and micronutrients in hydroponic systems (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Mn, and Zn). Optimizing plant output might potentially be achieved by precise control of wavelength and irradiance of PPF. It concludes that B up to a limit of 40% combined with R light 60 % is effective. Blue LED light is more than 50%, it will cause growth reduction. The effect of LED light on plant growth is varies, complex and challenging, due to influenced by the sensitivity of each plant species, the optimal proportion wavelength of red and blue light, the distance of LED and plant, overlapping of several types of photoreceptors, and development circumstances. Through this agricultural strategy, LED-equipped facilities maximize crop production efficiency and become a solution for obtaining quality crops with high nutritional value and abundant annual harvests with homogeneous and predictable results. Thus, integrating LED technology into modern agricultural practices may strongly contribute to sustainable agriculture.

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